

Siitonen, V., Ritonummi, S., Salo, M., Pirkkalainen, H., Mauno, S. (2024). Coping with Technostress in the Software Industry: Coping Strategies and Factors Underlying their Selection (Online Replication Package) (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14180104>

Exclusion criterion	Justification¹	Number excluded
Reported strain either “low” or “very low” on a 5-point Likert scale.	Response signaling the non-criticality of the incident, thus conflicting with the aim of our study.	44
Employment status reported as “Full-time student.”	Response unrelated to the working context of the software industry, thus conflicting with the aim of our study.	39
Response unrelated to the use of IT.	Response not describing a critical IT use incident, thus conflicting with the aim of our study	27
No sufficient detail in the description of the stressful incident or coping effort.	To ensure data quality by not including a response that did not allow capturing meaningful insights into the respondent’s stressful experience and coping efforts.	25
Failed attention check question.	To ensure data quality by not including a response that demonstrated not paying attention or not comprehending questionnaire instructions.	2
		Total 137

¹Study aim and context summarized: understand coping with critical stressful incidents caused by IT use at work in the software industry.